

Influence of advection on the soil gas radon deficit technique for the quantification of LNAPL

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HIGHLIGHTS

- The influence of advective transport on the Rn deficit technique is investigated.
- A 2-layer analytical model for Rn diffusive-advective transport was used.
- The analytical solution was validated against a numerical model.
- Local advective fluxes can significantly influence the Rn deficit.
- Neglecting advection can lead to an underestimation of the expected LNAPL saturation.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

The Radon (Rn) deficit technique is a rapid, low-cost, and non-invasive method to identify and quantify light non-aqueous phase liquids (LNAPL) in the soil. LNAPL saturation is typically estimated from Rn deficit using Rn partition coefficients, assuming equilibrium conditions. This work examines the applicability of this method in the presence of local advective fluxes that can be generated by groundwater fluctuations or biodegradation processes in the source zone. To this end, a one-dimensional analytical model was developed to simulate the steady-state diffusive-advective transport of soil gas Rn in the presence of LNAPL. The analytical solution was first validated against an existing numerical model adapted to include advection. Then a series of simulations to study the effect of advection on Rn profiles were carried out. It was found that in high-permeability soils (such as sandy soils), advective phenomena can significantly affect Rn deficit curves in the subsurface compared with those expected, assuming either equilibrium conditions or a diffusion-dominated transport. Namely, in the presence of pressure gradients generated by groundwater fluctuations, applying the traditional Rn deficit technique (assuming equilibrium conditions) can lead to an underestimation of LNAPL saturation. Furthermore, in the presence of methanogenesis processes (e.g., in the case of a fresh LNAPL of petroleum hydrocarbons), local advective fluxes can be expected above the source zone. In such cases, Rn concentrations above the source zone can be higher than those above background areas without advective phenomena, resulting in Rn deficits higher than 1 (i.e., Rn excess), and thus leading to a wrong interpretation regarding the presence of LNAPL in the subsurface if advection is not considered. Overall, the results obtained suggest that advection should be considered in the presence of pressure gradients in the subsurface to ensure an effective application of the soil gas Rn-deficit technique for quantitative estimation of LNAPL saturation.

1. Introduction

The issue of petroleum hydrocarbon contamination in the form of light non-aqueous phase liquids (LNAPL) accumulations in the subsurface is a

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Nomenclature

C	Rn activity concentration in soil gas, Bq/m ³
C _N	Rn concentration at the interface between the vadose zone and the vadose zone with residual LNAPL, Bq/m ³
C _{Ra}	²²⁶ Ra concentration of the solids, Bq/kg
D _e	Effective diffusion coefficient of Rn, m ² /s
D _{mg}	Rn molecular diffusion coefficient in the gas phase, m ² /s
D _{mw}	Rn molecular diffusion coefficient in the water phase, m ² /s
dp/dz	Pressure gradient, kg/m ² /s ²
f	Fraction of Rn in the gas phase, –
H _N	Thickness of the source zone, m
k _{g/w}	Rn partition coefficient between gas and water (Henry's law constant), –
k _{g/N}	Rn partition coefficient between gas and LNAPL (calculated as k _{g/w} /k _{N/w}), –
k _{int}	Intrinsic permeability, m ²
k _{N/w}	Rn partition coefficient between LNAPL and water, –
k _g	Effective permeability to soil gas flow, m ²
k _s	Soil saturated hydraulic conductivity, m/s
k _{s/w}	Rn partition coefficient between the solid and water, –
k _{rg}	Relative air permeability, m ²
L _W	Total profile length (water table depth), m
L _c	Rn characteristic diffusion length, m
L _N	Source zone depth, m
P	Rn production rate in the pore space, Bq/m ³ /s
S _N	LNAPL saturation, –
u	Upward soil gas velocity, m/s
z _{GW}	Depth of the groundwater table, m
z _N	Depth of the source zone, m
ε	Rn emanation coefficient, –
θ _g	Volumetric gas content, –
θ _N	Volumetric LNAPL content, –
θ _t	Total porosity, –
θ _w	Volumetric water content, –
λ	Rn first order decay constant, s ⁻¹
μ	Dynamic viscosity of soil gas, kg/m/s
ρ _s	Solid density, kg/m ³

widely spread and studied environmental problem (CL:AIRE, 2014). LNAPL is a complex mixture of hydrocarbon compounds (and minor, but not negligible polar compounds containing sulfur, nitrogen, and oxygen) often characterized by an accumulation near the water table interface (CL:AIRE, 2014), in the form of mobile (free product) or immobile residual phase (ITRC, 2018).

There are several in situ methods for detecting the presence of LNAPL in soil. The traditional techniques typically involve the analysis of soil samples in the saturated and unsaturated zone or the monitoring of the thickness of the free product observed in monitoring wells (Newell et al., 1995). Both methods typically provide limited information on the LNAPL contamination in terms of spatial resolution of the impacted area (ITRC, 2018). Furthermore, by only monitoring the free product observed in monitoring wells, it is not possible to quantify the residual LNAPL phase. Newer methods, which can provide more accurate information but are economically more expensive, are in situ direct-push techniques such as the Membrane Interface Probe (MIP) or the Laser-Induced Fluorescence (LIF) (ITRC, 2019). The need to increase the accuracy of the characterization and decrease the time, invasiveness, and cost of the techniques used, has led to the development of innovative approaches, such as the use of tracers, or the adaptation of existing non-invasive techniques, such as soil gas analysis (García-González et al., 2008).

Rn is the inert radioactive gas continuously produced by the alpha decay of radium (²²⁶Ra) in the natural decay of the uranium (²³⁸U) series

(Sakoda et al., 2011). The radium content of the soil, given as an activity concentration per unit mass, is equivalent to the total production rate of Rn in the soil, but only a fraction of the Rn generated leaves the solid grains and enters the pore volume of the soil (Nazaroff, 1992). This fraction is known as the emanation coefficient. In uncontaminated soil, Rn in the subsurface is mainly distributed among three states: a phase sorbed onto the surface of soil grains, a phase dissolved in the water contained in the soil pores, and a phase dispersed within the gas in the soil pores (Nazaroff et al., 1989). In the presence of LNAPL in the soil, Rn will also partition into this additional phase. Despite its virtually inert behavior, Rn generally shows good solubility in a wide range of LNAPL, as several authors have ascertained (e.g., Clever, 1979; Schubert et al., 2001). Because of its preferential partitioning into organic phases (Nazaroff, 1992; Hunkeler et al., 1997; Semprini et al., 2000), the subsurface LNAPL contamination can influence the natural concentration of Rn in soil gas (Schubert et al., 2001). The dimensionless LNAPL/air and LNAPL/water partition coefficients are the most influential parameters governing the partitioning of Rn and, thus, its concentration in the soil gas in the presence of a subsurface LNAPL contamination (Le Meur et al., 2021). Specifically, Rn concentrations in soil gas are expected to decrease in areas impacted by LNAPL compared to background values in uncontaminated zones, creating a measurable Rn deficit. This phenomenon can be used, by means of a method known as the 'radon deficit technique' (Semprini et al., 2000; Schubert et al., 2001), to identify LNAPL contamination in the subsurface. For this reason, Rn has been the focus of many studies on the characterization of LNAPL-contaminated sites from a practical and a modeling point of view. Several studies (see Hunkeler et al., 1997; Schubert et al., 2005; Fan et al., 2007; Barbosa et al., 2014; Mateus and Pecequillo, 2015; Cohen et al., 2016; Castelluccio et al., 2018; De Miguel et al., 2018; De Miguel et al., 2020; Barrio-Parra et al., 2021) are available on the field applications of the technique. For instance, concerning soil gas applications, Schubert et al. (2002) indicated a good performance of the method to identify an area with the presence of free-phase kerosene, highlighting, however, the limitations related to geological complexities and the characteristic diffusion length of Rn. García-González et al. (2008) spatially analyzed the observed reduction of Rn concentration in soil gas at a site, estimating a surface contour of the NAPL source zone, which agreed well with the free phase thickness measurements taken in the site's monitoring wells. Barbosa et al. (2014) correlated, at a site where a gasoline leak occurred, Rn concentrations in soil gas with volatile organic compounds (VOCs) detected at the same locations, and although the highest VOCs concentration was at the area with the lowest Rn concentration, it was also stated that, considering the whole investigated site, the correlation was not significant between the two parameters. Similar conclusions were also drawn by Castelluccio et al. (2018). The results of seven field campaigns carried out at one site, described by Barrio-Parra et al. (2021), showed a good correlation between the points of low Rn concentration and the areas of highest contamination in the top soil layers, although the same conclusions could not be drawn for the contamination of the deeper soil layers. In general, a good potential of the method is observed, although with some aspects to be further investigated for optimal realisation. Regarding modeling, major efforts have focused on predicting Rn profiles in water (see Semprini et al., 2000; Davis et al., 2005; Schubert et al., 2007) and soil gas (see Höhener and Surbeck, 2004; Cohen et al., 2019; Barrio-Parra et al., 2022; Cecconi et al., 2022) under various site-specific conditions, focusing on the issues of Rn emanation, partition, and transport.

Diffusion is commonly considered the dominant transport process for the migration of gases in the vadose zone (Hillel, 1982). Indeed, on a long-term average basis, available evidence suggests that Rn transport from the soil into the atmosphere occurs predominantly by molecular diffusion (Nazaroff, 1992). However, under certain conditions, pressure-driven advection may also be significant (Alzaydi et al., 1978; Thorstenson and Pollock, 1989; Massmann and Farrier, 1992; US EPA, 2015). In particular, advection may be the locally dominant flow in the presence of high average pressure or when intermolecular collisions prevail over collisions between gas molecules and pore walls (Cunningham and Williams, 1980). The latter

condition can occur when the average free path of gas molecules is much smaller than the pore size of the medium, e.g., in dry, coarse-grained media (Scanlon et al., 2002).

Several factors can induce a local pressure gradient in the soil that causes an advective flow (Molins and Mayer, 2007; US EPA, 2015). Cyclic fluctuations in barometric pressure (caused by diurnal temperature variations and the passage of high and low-pressure fronts) cause an inward and outward advective motion of subsurface air (Forde et al., 2019), known as barometric pumping (Auer et al., 1996). However, this phenomenon only affects the surface soil layers, typically around the first meter. According to Neznal et al. (2004), a sampling depth of 0.8 m is a good compromise between reducing the effect of atmospheric phenomena and the practicality of measurements with temporary probes. Assuming, therefore, that Rn measurements are performed at these or greater depths, the influence of barometric fluctuations and the resulting advective flow can be considered irrelevant to the application under discussion.

Another phenomenon that can lead to the generation of an advective flow in the subsurface is the fluctuations of the water table induced by various periodic natural forces (Man et al., 2021). Groundwater fluctuations can cause upward and downward advection of soil gas within the vadose zone, promoting the transport of soil gases and accelerating the vapor phase transport through the unsaturated zone and their release into the atmosphere (Qi et al., 2020). In fact, a drop in the water table level can create a reduction in total gas pressure, producing a suction effect that can limit the gas flow, while the upward movement of groundwater creates an increase in total gas pressure, resulting in a piston effect that pushes the soil gases toward the surface (Cavelan et al., 2022). Choi and Smith (2005) investigated the effects of water table fluctuations on advective and diffusive fluxes of volatile organic compounds under natural atmospheric conditions and suggested that water table fluctuation with an amplitude of 0.1 m can create pressure gradients in the soil similar in magnitude to those caused by atmospheric pressure variations, which could significantly affect the advective flux. Man et al. (2021) showed that soil texture plays a significant role in the advective transport of soil gas. Other phenomena that can create a local advective flow in the subsurface can be related to LNAPL contamination (Ma et al., 2012; Yao et al., 2015; Verginelli and Baciocchi, 2021). A significant in-situ generation of CH₄ can make advection the dominant local gas transport mechanism (Yao et al., 2015; CRC CARE, 2018). Methanogenesis is now accepted as one of the dominant attenuation processes of LNAPL sources (e.g., Lundegard and Johnson, 2006; Ng et al., 2015; ITRC, 2009; CRC CARE, 2018). Significant methanogenesis can occur, under anaerobic conditions, in the saturated zone and at the bottom of the unsaturated zone, which results in direct outgassing and ebullition of methane and carbon dioxide (ITRC, 2018). The combined gas fluxes migrate vertically upward through the unsaturated zone, where methane is oxidized (Amos et al., 2005). In accordance with

field observations, the zones of CH₄ generation (near the water table and oil body) correlate with slightly elevated total gas pressures, while above the methanogenic zone, in the methanotrophic zone, CH₄ and O₂ consumption causes gas pressure to decrease marginally below atmospheric levels (Molins et al., 2010). Furthermore, the solubility of CO₂, produced in the methane oxidation reaction, is higher than that of O₂ or CH₄, so even more gas is removed from the gas phase by the dissolution of the produced gas into water (Amos et al., 2005).

Since advection, compared to diffusion, can transfer Rn over a wide range of distances it is important to account for this phenomenon when applying the soil gas Rn deficit technique. Indeed, if not properly considered, the existence of advective phenomena can result in a further confounding factor for the interpretation of the Rn deficit detected in soil gas. For instance, De Miguel et al. (2018) found, during a field campaign, Rn concentrations above background values in an area where other evidence indicated the presence of NAPL. Mateus and Pecequilo (2015) successfully identified NAPL contamination in some areas by monitoring Rn in the upper soil, but also found high Rn values, compared to the site average, in some areas where a NAPL plume was estimated to exist. Cohen et al. (2016) found unclear correlations between Rn and NAPL at another site where methane was also found in the soil gas, explaining these results by the presence of stratigraphic heterogeneities. Although the anomalous behavior observed in the above-mentioned works would require further investigations to be explained, as suggested by De Miguel et al. (2018), a possible partial explanation could be given by the establishment of advective phenomena, especially in cases where other parameters might indicate its possible occurrence (e.g., the methane detected in the field campaigns carried out by Cohen et al. (2016)).

To account for the aspects described above, this work aims to evaluate the impact of the advective term on the transport of Rn in the soil gas in soils characterized by the presence of LNAPL. For this purpose, a 1-D steady-state analytical solution of the equation for the diffusive-advective transport of Rn in the subsurface in a two-layer soil was developed. To our knowledge, no analytical models that allow to account for both diffusion and advection of Rn in the subsurface in the presence of LNAPL are available in the literature. The developed 2-layer analytical solution estimates the vertical concentration profiles of Rn in soil gas at a steady state in a two-layer soil, assuming a diffusive-advective transport of Rn. The validity of the solution has been tested by comparing the results with an already existing numerical model (Barrio-Parra et al., 2022), that was adapted in this work to include the advective term. The analytical solution was then used to study the influence of the advective term on Rn profiles and, consequently, on the Rn deficit, carrying out simulations under different conditions of pressure gradient and contamination, and considering the influence of other site-specific parameters.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Governing equation and assumptions

The analytical model was developed assuming a 1-D steady-state advective-diffusion transport of Rn in homogeneous soils. The solution was obtained under assumptions consistent with previous Rn modeling studies (e.g., Höhener and Surbeck, 2004; Cohen et al., 2019). In particular, a homogeneous soil, a constant diffusion coefficient, and a constant advective velocity were considered for each layer. A constant and uniform emanation of Rn from the solid matrix was also considered. Furthermore, Rn decay was assumed to be the only reaction to occur and was described by a first-order decay constant (λ). The phenomenon of Rn partitioning between soil phases (solid phase, gas, water, and LNAPL) was considered instantaneous and reversible and was described by linear equilibrium partitioning constants (Werner and Höhener, 2002).

Under the above assumptions, the governing equation for the diffusive and advective steady-state transport of Rn in a homogeneous layer i of unsaturated soil is:

$$f_i D_{e,i} \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial z^2} - f_i u_i \frac{\partial C}{\partial z} - \lambda C + f_i P_i = 0 \quad (1)$$

where C is the Rn activity concentration in soil gas (Bq/m³); $D_{e,i}$ is the effective diffusion coefficient of Rn in layer i (m²/s); f_i (–) is the fraction of Rn in the air phase of layer i ; u_i is the soil gas velocity (m/s); P_i is the Rn production rate in the pore space in layer i (Bq/m³/s).

The effective diffusion coefficient of Rn in layer i , $D_{e,i}$ can be calculated using the expression proposed by Millington and Quirk (1961):

$$D_{e,i} = D_{m,g} \frac{\theta_{g,i}^{10/3}}{\theta_{t,i}^2} + D_{m,w} \frac{\theta_{w,i}^{10/3}}{k_{g/w} \theta_{t,i}^2} \tag{2}$$

where $\theta_{t,i}$ is the total soil porosity in layer i , $\theta_{g,i}$ is the volumetric gas content in layer i , $\theta_{w,i}$ is the volumetric water content in layer i , $D_{m,g}$ and $D_{m,w}$ are Rn molecular diffusion coefficients (m^2/s) in the gas and water phases, respectively, and $k_{g/w}$ is Rn gas-water partition coefficient (i.e., the dimensionless Henry's law constant).

The fraction of Rn in the air phase of layer i , f_i (–), can be written as (Werner and Höhener, 2002):

$$f_i = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{\rho_s(1 - \theta_{t,i})k_{s/w}}{k_{g/w}\theta_{g,i}} + \frac{\theta_{w,i}}{k_{g/w}\theta_{g,i}} + \frac{\theta_{N,i}}{k_{g/N}\theta_{g,i}}} \tag{3}$$

where $\theta_{N,i}$ is the volumetric LNAPL content of layer i , ρ_s is the solid density (kg/m^3), $k_{s/w}$ is Rn solid-water partition coefficient, and $k_{g/N}$ is Rn gas-NAPL partition coefficient.

The Rn production rate in the pore space in layer i , P_i ($Bq/m^3/s$), can be calculated as follows (Van der Spoel et al., 1997):

$$P_i = \frac{C_{Ra} \lambda \epsilon \rho_s (1 - \theta_{t,i})}{\theta_{g,i}} \tag{4}$$

with C_{Ra} the ^{226}Ra concentration of the solids (Bq/kg), λ the Rn first order decay constant ($1/s$), and ϵ (–) the Rn emanation coefficient.

The soil gas velocity u_i can be estimated using the following equation (Scanlon et al., 2002):

$$u_i = \frac{k_{g,i}}{\mu} \frac{dp_i}{dz} \tag{5}$$

where $k_{g,i}$ (m^2) is the effective permeability to soil gas flow, μ ($kg/m/s$) is the dynamic viscosity of soil gas, and dp_i/dz ($kg/m^2/s^2$) is the pressure variation, also synthetically denoted by ∇p_i . The effective permeability $k_{g,i}$ can be calculated as the product of the intrinsic permeability $k_{int,i}$ (m^2) and the relative air permeability $k_{r,g,i}$ (–) at the soil water-filled porosity $\theta_{w,i}$:

$$k_{g,i} = k_{int,i} \cdot k_{r,g,i} \tag{6}$$

Note that all parameters with the subscript i depend on the soil layer's characteristics.

2.2. Analytical solution

For heterogeneous layered soils, but without the advective term, Eq. (1) has been solved analytically by Höhener and Surbeck (2004) and Cecconi et al. (2022). In this work, we present an analytical solution for a 2-layer model that can be used to describe both the diffusive and advective transport of Rn in a contaminated layer (source zone) and the overlying unsaturated layer.

Fig. 1. Domain of the 2-layer model consisting of an upper layer of uncontaminated vadose zone and a deeper layer of vadose zone with the presence of LNAPL. The origin of axis z is placed at ground level and is positive with increasing depth. The figure also describes the boundary conditions assumed to derive the analytical solution and the conditions that may cause advective phenomena in the soil (water table fluctuations and methanogenesis processes).

The domain of the 2-layer model developed in this work is depicted in Fig. 1. The domain was divided into two zones: a non-contaminated layer of the vadose zone and an underlying layer of the vadose zone with LNAPL. To solve Eq. (1), three boundary conditions were considered (see Fig. 1). Specifically, the Rn concentration was considered zero in air (Höhener and Surbeck, 2004), the continuity of concentration was imposed at the interface between the two layers and no Rn flux was assumed at the water table depth ($z = L_w$).

By imposing these boundary conditions, the following solutions describing the Rn concentration profile in the domain were derived:

$$C(z) = \begin{cases} C_N \left(\frac{e^{-k_V(L_N - z)} \sinh(\gamma_V z)}{\sinh(\gamma_V L_N)} \right) + \frac{P_V f_V}{\lambda} \left(1 - \frac{e^{k_V z} \sinh(\gamma_V(L_N - z)) + e^{-k_V(L_N - z)} \sinh(\gamma_V z)}{\sinh(\gamma_V L_N)} \right) & \text{for } 0 \leq z \leq L_N \\ \left(C_N - \frac{P_N f_N}{\lambda} \right) \left[\frac{e^{-k_N(L_N - z)} [k_N \sinh(\gamma_N(L_w - z)) + \gamma_N \cosh(\gamma_N(L_w - z))]}{[k_N \sinh(\gamma_N(L_w - L_N)) + \gamma_N \cosh(\gamma_N(L_w - L_N))]} \right] + \frac{P_N f_N}{\lambda} & \text{for } L_N < z \leq L_w \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Fig. 2. Conceptual model of the four simulated scenarios: a) purely diffusive transport both in the LNAPL zone and background area, b) rising water table both in the LNAPL zone and background area (positive pressure gradient, advective flux toward the surface), c) falling water table both in the LNAPL zone and background area (negative pressure gradient, downward advective flux), d) presence of fresh LNAPL in the LNAPL zone (positive pressure gradient in the LNAPL source zone (Ns) due to CH₄ production and negative pressure gradient in the overlying zone (Nu) due to CH₄ oxidation) and no advective flux in the background zone (diffusive flux only).

Table 1

Parameters used for the validation of the analytical model (Fig. 3) and to derive the vertical Rn concentration profiles and the Rn deficit curves in Figs. 4–8 (unless otherwise indicated in the figures).

Parameter	Symbol	Unit	Values (Figs. 3–8)
Solid density	ρ_s	kg/m ³	1660
Soil type	–	–	Sand
Total porosity	θ_t	–	0.375
Water saturation	θ_w	–	0.054
Relative air permeability	k_{rg}	–	0.998
Intrinsic permeability	k_i	m ²	10^{-10}
Effective permeability	k_g	m ²	$9.98 \cdot 10^{-11}$
Dynamic viscosity of soil gas	μ	kg/m/s	$1.8 \cdot 10^{-6}$
Rn partition coefficient between soil and water	$k_{s/w}$	–	$1.4 \cdot 10^{-5}$
Rn partition coefficient between gas and water (Henry's law constant)	$k_{g/w}$	–	4.4
Contamination	–	–	Diesel
Rn partition coefficient between NAPL and water	$k_{N/w}$	–	60
Rn first order decay constant	λ	1/s	$2.1 \cdot 10^{-6}$
²²⁶ Ra concentration of the solids	C_{Ra}	Bq/kg	30
Rn emanation coefficient	ε	–	0.2
Rn molecular diffusion coefficient in the gas phase	D_{mg}	m ² /s	$1.1 \cdot 10^{-5}$
Rn molecular diffusion coefficient in the water phase	D_{mw}	m ² /s	$1.1 \cdot 10^{-9}$
Total profile length	L	m	5
Source zone depth	L_N	m	4
Thickness of the source zone	H_N	m	1
NAPL saturation	S_N	%	10
Time interval (numerical model)	dt	s	60
Depth interval (numerical model)	dz	m	0.05
Simulation duration (numerical model)	t_{max}	days	30
Lower boundary (numerical model)	Boundary	–	Open

where k_i is calculated as:

$$k_i = \frac{u}{2D_{e,i}} \tag{8}$$

and γ_i calculated as:

$$\gamma_i = \sqrt{\frac{u^2}{4D_{e,i}^2} + \frac{\lambda}{f_i D_{e,i}}} = \sqrt{k_i^2 + \frac{1}{L_{c,i}^2}} \tag{9}$$

with $L_{c,i}$ the characteristic diffusion length of Rn in layer i :

$$L_{c,i} = \sqrt{\frac{f_i D_{e,i}}{\lambda}} \tag{10}$$

Next, by imposing the continuity of the fluxes at the interface of the contiguous layers, the expression of the concentration C_N (at $z = L_N$) was derived. The resulting expression is given in the following equation:

$$C_N = \frac{D_{e,v} \frac{P_v f_v}{\lambda} \left(k_v + \gamma_v \coth(\gamma_v L_N) - \frac{\gamma_v e^{\lambda L_N}}{\sinh(\gamma_v L_N)} \right) - D_{e,N} \frac{P_N f_N}{\lambda} \frac{k_N k_N - \gamma_N \gamma_N}{[k_N + \gamma_N \coth(\gamma_N (L_w - L_N))]} }{D_{e,v} (k_v + \gamma_v \coth(\gamma_v L_N)) - D_{e,N} \frac{k_N k_N - \gamma_N \gamma_N}{[k_N + \gamma_N \coth(\gamma_N (L_w - L_N))]} } \tag{11}$$

The developed analytical solution was applied to calculate the vertical Rn concentration profiles under different scenarios. In particular, the Rn profile in the NAPL zone was calculated and compared to that expected under the same conditions but at a background location not impacted by the LNAPL. From the

Table 2

Surface pressure gradient conditions in the subsurface considered to derive the vertical Rn concentration profiles and the Rn deficit curves in Figs. 4–8 (unless otherwise indicated in the figures).

Scenario	Zone	Symbol	Unit	Pressure gradient values (Figs. 4–8)		
				Low	Medium	High
Rising water table (Fig. 2b)	NAPL zone, upper layer	$\nabla p N_u$	Pa/m	0.01	0.05	0.1
	NAPL zone, source zone	$\nabla p N_s$	Pa/m	0.01	0.05	0.1
	Background area	$\nabla p B$	Pa/m	0.01	0.05	0.1
Falling water table (Fig. 2c)	NAPL zone, upper layer	$\nabla p N_u$	Pa/m	–0.01	–0.05	–0.1
	NAPL zone, source zone	$\nabla p N_s$	Pa/m	–0.01	–0.05	–0.1
	Background area	$\nabla p B$	Pa/m	–0.01	–0.05	–0.1
Fresh LNAPL (Fig. 2d)	NAPL zone, upper layer	$\nabla p N_u$	Pa/m	–0.0025	–0.0125	–0.025
	NAPL zone, source zone	$\nabla p N_s$	Pa/m	0.01	0.05	0.1
	Background area	$\nabla p B$	Pa/m	0	0	0

Fig. 3. Rn concentration profiles for different imposed pressure gradients calculated with the analytical model (continuous lines) and the numerical model (dots) adapted from Barrio-Parra et al. (2022). Four imposed pressure gradients are shown: zero pressure gradient, i.e., diffusion-dominated transport (figure a); constant positive pressure gradient of +0.1 Pa/m (figure b); constant negative pressure gradient of -0.1 Pa/m (figure c); variable pressure gradient of +0.1 Pa/m in the LNAPL layer and of -0.025 in the overlying vadose zone layer (figure d). The dashed lines represent the beginning of the layer with the presence of LNAPL. A LNAPL saturation of 10% in the deepest layer was imposed. The performance of the analytical model is shown for each simulation in terms of coefficient of determination R^2 and normalized root mean square error NRMSE.

ratio of these two concentration profiles, the expected deficit profiles under the specific conditions of each case were derived. Rn deficit was calculated at each depth as:

$$Deficit(z) = \frac{C_{LNAPL}(z)}{C_{NONAPL}(z)} \tag{12}$$

where $C_{LNAPL}(z)$ is the Rn concentration at depth z in the presence of LNAPL and $C_{NONAPL}(z)$ is the Rn concentration at the same depth z in the absence of LNAPL.

2.3. Simulated scenarios and input parameters

The analytical solution was applied to assess the role of advection in different scenarios where, under certain conditions, a subsurface pressure gradient can be expected. The scenarios investigated comprise the condition of a rising water table, which creates a positive pressure gradient and a resultant advective flux toward the surface (Fig. 2b), the condition of a falling water table, with a negative pressure gradient creating a downward advective flux (Fig. 2c), and the case of the presence of fresh LNAPL, with a positive pressure gradient in the zone with LNAPL due to methanogenesis and a negative pressure gradient in the overlying zone of methane oxidation (Fig. 2d). In this latter case, since the pressure gradient affects only the contaminated zone, a purely diffusive transport was considered in the background area. The case of purely diffusive transport will be used as a comparison (see Fig. 2a). The scenarios

Fig. 4. Rn concentration profiles and Rn deficit curves for different imposed pressure gradients, simulating the condition of groundwater level elevation in both the LNAPL zone (denoted with N_u for the upper layer and N_s for the LNAPL source zone) and background (denoted with B). Four pressure gradient values are shown: zero pressure gradient, i.e., purely diffusive transport (figure a); a pressure gradient of 0.01 Pa/m (figure b), 0.05 Pa/m (figure c) and 0.1 Pa/m (figure d). The dashed lines represent the beginning of the layer with the presence of LNAPL. LNAPL saturation in the deepest layer is imposed at 10 %.

described in Fig. 2b and c are more likely to occur at sites near coastal areas or in tropical climates subject to heavy rainfall in short periods of time. The scenario described in Fig. 2d, on the other hand, can be considered characteristic of areas with high LNAPL saturation levels and fresh LNAPL, which are more likely to result in high methane production.

The input parameters listed in Tables 1 and 2 were used for the simulations shown in the following sections. The values of characteristic soil parameters (e.g., porosity, density, water saturation) given by US EPA (2004) were used in all simulations. Details regarding the estimation of the intrinsic permeability and the relative air permeability are given in the Supplementary Material 1.

3. Results

3.1. Comparison with a numerical model

Fig. 3 shows a comparison of the steady-state Rn concentration profiles predicted by the analytical solution developed in this work (continuous lines) with the results obtained using the numerical model (points) developed by Barrio-Parra et al. (2022). For the analytical model, the solution previously described was used (Eqs. (7), (11)). For the numerical model, the original Matlab® code developed by Barrio-Parra et al. (2022) has been adapted to account for the advective transport (the full Matlab® code is available in the

Supplementary Material). Four scenarios representing different pressure gradient conditions were simulated using the same input parameters reported in Table 1. Note that for the transient numerical model, the Rn concentration profiles represent the results obtained assuming a 30-day simulation which, according to preliminary simulations, was found to be representative of steady-state conditions. From Fig. 3, it can be observed that there is a good agreement between the numerical results and those predicted with the analytical model developed in this work. The performance of the analytical model were evaluated by the coefficient of determination R^2 and the normalized root mean square error (NRMSE). Specifically, the R^2 value was 0.999 for all simulations, and the NRMSE was always lower than 1.5 % (0.015) (see

Fig. 3). These values indicate an accurate model simulation, thus confirming the validity of the analytical model to simulate the expected Rn concentration profiles in the presence of a pressure gradient in the subsurface.

3.2. Influence of the pressure gradient on Rn deficit profiles

The developed analytical solution was used to examine the Rn concentration profiles expected in the presence of pressure gradients in the subsurface at LNAPL-impacted areas and in background locations not impacted by LNAPL. From the ratio of these two concentration profiles, the expected Rn deficit curves were also calculated (see Eq. (12)). Unless otherwise stated, the site-specific parameters used in the simulations are those reported in Table 1, and the pressure gradient conditions considered are those summarized in Table 2.

3.2.1. Positive pressure gradient (rising water table)

Fig. 4 shows the Rn concentration profiles and the relative Rn deficits obtained assuming a positive pressure gradient in the subsurface (see

Fig. 2b). The pressure gradient values simulated in Fig. 4b, c and d (see Table 2) are representative of a water table rise between approximately 0.3 cm and 3 cm in a period of 0.5 days, assuming a sandy soil ($k_g = 4.04 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ m}^2$, $\theta_{a,cap} = 0.045$) and according to the method reported by Choi and Smith (2005). In Fig. 4a the Rn profiles in the case of a purely diffusive transport over the whole soil thickness (zero-pressure gradient i.e., no advective transport) are shown. As can be observed, the Rn concentration profiles obtained assuming a pressure gradient in the subsurface can be substantially different from the one expected assuming a purely diffusive transport. It can also be observed that as the pressure gradient increases there is a smaller deviation between the Rn concentration curves in the contaminated zone and the background zone (i.e. Rn deficit tends to 1). Indeed, a positive pressure gradient increases the velocity of soil gas flow toward the soil surface, reducing the attenuation of Rn caused by its partitioning into the LNAPL. It may be assumed, for example, to sample soil gas in proximity of the LNAPL source, e.g. considering the top of the source zone (in the present case at a distance of 1 m from the water table). Although,

Fig. 5. Rn concentration profiles and Rn deficit curves for different imposed pressure gradients, simulating the condition of lowering groundwater level in both the LNAPL zone (denoted with N_u for the upper layer and N_s for the LNAPL source zone) and background (denoted with B). Four pressure gradient values are shown: zero pressure gradient, i.e., purely diffusive transport (figure a); a pressure gradient of -0.01 Pa/m (figure b), -0.05 Pa/m (figure c) and -0.1 Pa/m (figure d). The dashed lines represent the beginning of the layer with the presence of LNAPL. LNAPL saturation in the deepest layer is imposed at 10 %.

depending on soil type, temporal probes can be used at depths up to 4–5 m, typically soil gas samples collected at depths greater than 2 m are not cost-effective with commonly used direct-push techniques. At 2 m depth, the Rn deficit expected in the simulated scenario for a diffusive-only transport is approximately equal to 0.66 (Fig. 4a), while in the case of a diffusive-advective transport the Rn deficit is 0.69, 0.82 and 0.9 in Fig. 4b, c and d, respectively. This implies that, under the conditions considered, the deficit values observable at the top of the source zone, assuming a positive subsurface pressure gradient, can be up to 1.3/1.4 times higher than the deficit observed at the same depth in the case of diffusive transport only. Note that these deficits result from Rn concentrations in the NAPL zone of approximately 12.2–13.7 kBq/m³ (corresponding to maximum differences of about 15%) and Rn background concentrations of 18.4–14.1 kBq/m³ (corresponding to maximum differences of about 25%) (for Fig. 4a, b, c and d

respectively). It is worth mentioning, that Rn concentration values can be significantly different, depending on the radium content and the Rn emanation coefficient (among other parameters) characteristic of the soil under investigation. It is also worth recalling that the deficit observed at a certain depth is used in the Rn deficit technique to estimate the subsurface residual LNAPL saturation. From these first results, it is evident that the presence of advective transport has a relevant impact on the interpretation of Rn monitoring data for the quantification of LNAPL contamination.

3.2.2. Negative pressure gradient (falling water table)

Fig. 5 shows Rn concentration profiles and the relative Rn deficits for a negative pressure gradient in the subsurface (see Fig. 2c). Fig. 5a shows the case of purely diffusive transport, while the profiles for diffusive-advective transport are shown in Fig. 5b, c and d, respectively. The simulated pressure

Fig. 6. Rn concentration profiles and Rn deficit curves for different imposed pressure gradients, simulating the condition of the presence of fresh LNAPL. Four pressure gradient conditions are shown: zero pressure gradient, i.e., purely diffusive transport in both the LNAPL (denoted with N_u for the upper layer and N_s for the LNAPL source zone) and background (denoted with B) zones, (figure a); a pressure gradient of +0.01 Pa/m in the LNAPL zone and -0.0025 Pa/m in the upper layer, and a zero pressure gradient in the background location (figure b), a pressure gradient of +0.05 Pa/m in the LNAPL zone and -0.0125 Pa/m in the upper layer, and a zero pressure gradient in the background location (figure c), a pressure gradient of +0.1 Pa/m in the LNAPL zone and -0.025 Pa/m in the upper layer, and a zero pressure gradient in the background location (figure d). The dashed lines represent the beginning of the layer with the presence of LNAPL. LNAPL saturation in the deepest layer is imposed at 10%.

gradient values (see Table 2) are representative of a drop in the groundwater level between 0.3 cm and 3 cm for a period of 0.5 days, assuming a sandy soil ($k_g = 4.04 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ m}^2$, $\theta_{a,\text{cap}} = 0.045$), using the method described by Choi and Smith (2005). As can be observed in Fig. 5, a negative pressure gradient limits the gas flow toward the surface, and thus leads to an increase of Rn attenuation due to the partitioning effect of Rn in the LNAPL present in the source zone. Therefore, it can be observed that as the negative pressure gradient increases, there is a more significant deviation between the Rn concentration profiles expected above the source and background zone. Considering, for example, the deficit value at the top of the source zone (at 1 m from the groundwater level), the Rn deficit expected in the simulated scenario for a diffusive transport (Fig. 5a) is approximately 0.66, while introducing a pressure gradient of respectively -0.01 , -0.05 and -0.1 Pa/m (Fig. 5b, c and d), the Rn deficit is 0.63, 0.52 and 0.46 (i.e. up to 1.4 times lower than the deficit expected for a diffusion-dominated transport). The effect of advection is less pronounced in the source zone, where the deficit profiles for a diffusion-dominated transport and for a diffusive-advective transport approach each other. This suggests that performing soil gas Rn measurements in proximity of the source zone can potentially be helpful in reducing the confounding effect of advection on the interpretation of Rn data for the identification and quantification of LNAPL in the subsoil. It should be noted, however, that drilling at great depths to collect soil gas samples could be practically complicated and/or economically unfeasible. To reach these depths, an alternative way may consist in measuring Rn soil gas concentration in the headspace of groundwater monitoring wells. This approach could, for example, be useful for monitoring the evolution of LNAPL contamination during natural attenuation processes or during active remediation.

3.2.3. Variable pressure gradient (fresh LNAPL)

Fig. 6 shows Rn concentration profiles simulated in the presence of fresh LNAPL (see Fig. 2d). In particular, Fig. 6b, c and d show the Rn deficit curves obtained by considering a diffusion-only transport in the background zone and a diffusive-advective transport in the area with the presence of LNAPL. The pressure gradient values assumed in the two zones for each figure are summarized in Table 2, and are consistent with literature values (Molins et al., 2010; Ma et al., 2014). Fig. 6a shows the case of diffusive-only transport in both zones as a reference. It can be observed that for shallow sampling depths, the values of Rn concentration in the LNAPL zone exceed the values of Rn concentration in the background zone, in contrast with what is typically expected. Considering that the Rn deficit is calculated (see Eq. (12)) as the ratio of the Rn concentration in the presence of LNAPL to the concentration of Rn in the background zone, the deficit value becomes at some depths greater than 1. It can be observed that as the pressure gradient is higher, the increase of Rn deficit values over 1 is observable at increasing depths. For the lower pressure gradient values (Fig. 6b), for instance, this effect is no longer visible for depths greater than 1 m, and even at those depths, the effect is almost negligible. This scenario highlights how the influence of advective transport can be significant and such that Rn profiles can, in some cases, be reversed from those expected. In such situations, using the Rn deficit technique without taking advection into account could entail the risk of misinterpreting the state of soil contamination. Also in these cases, however, performing Rn measurements at greater depths (ideally in the proximity of the LNAPL source zone) can reduce the risk of misinterpreting Rn deficit data for LNAPL detection and localization.

3.3. Influence of pressure gradient on the estimation of LNAPL saturation

Fig. 7 shows the Rn deficit curves calculated assuming a LNAPL saturation of 5 % (Fig. 7a, d, and g), 10 % (Fig. 7b, e and h), and 20 % (Fig. 7c, f, and i) (typical residual saturation range according to API (2000)), considering the pressure gradient conditions described in Fig. 2 and the values indicated in Table 2. The diffusive Rn deficit curve and three diffusive-advective deficit curves (lower, intermediate and higher pressure gradient value) are shown in each graph. In the case of a positive pressure gradient

(Fig. 7a–c), the deficit at the top of the source zone (at 1 m from the water table) is higher for diffusive-advective transport than for purely diffusive transport (shown in the same figures with the dashed line) by a factor up to 1.2, 1.4 and 1.5 (LNAPL saturations of 5 %, 10 % and 20 % respectively). Considering, for example, the deficit curve in Fig. 7a ($S_N = 5 \%$) representing a positive pressure gradient of 0.05 Pa/m , the observed deficit in the upper part of the source zone is approximately 0.88. If the advective term were ignored, using this deficit value would lead to estimating a LNAPL saturation of about 2 % (using the nomographs presented by Cecconi et al. (2022)). This means that in the proposed example, ignoring the presence of advective transport would result in underestimating LNAPL saturation by more than 2 times. It should also be noted that the Rn deficit technique is typically applied (e.g., Schubert et al., 2001; Schubert, 2015; De Simone et al., 2017; Castelluccio et al., 2018) assuming equilibrium conditions (i.e. neglecting both diffusion and advection):

$$Deficit_{eq} = \frac{\theta_{g, \text{NONAPL}} + \frac{\theta_{w, \text{NONAPL}}}{k_{g/w}}}{\theta_{g, \text{NAPL}} + \frac{\theta_{w, \text{NAPL}}}{k_{g/w}} + \frac{\theta_N}{k_{g/N}}} \quad (13)$$

By comparing the deficits obtained in Fig. 7a, b and c, with the expected deficit at equilibrium conditions (shown as reference in each figure), it can be noticed that in the case of positive pressure gradients the presence of advection compared to diffusion alone causes the deficit values to deviate even further from equilibrium conditions. For example, using again a Rn deficit of 0.88 at the source zone (relative to a positive pressure gradient of 0.05 Pa/m for a LNAPL saturation of 5 %), would result in an estimated LNAPL saturation of 0.5 % (Eq. (13)) considering equilibrium conditions. These considerations indicate that, in the proposed example, assuming equilibrium conditions and thus ignoring the presence of both diffusive and advective transport would result in an estimate of LNAPL saturation 10 times lower than the actual one.

The same conclusions can be drawn by considering the curves in Fig. 8, which show LNAPL saturation calculated as a function of the Rn deficit obtained considering soil gas Rn measurements carried out at a fixed distance from the water table. In particular, different saturation-deficit curves are shown assuming a rising water table, a falling water table, and the presence of fresh LNAPL (respectively Fig. 8a–c, d–f and g–i) and performing Rn measurements at the water table (Fig. 8a, d, g), at a vertical distance of 1 m from it (Fig. 8b, e, h) and at a distance of 4 m (Fig. 8c, f, i). Each graph shows three saturation-deficit curves: under equilibrium conditions (using Eq. (13)), under diffusive transport conditions, and under diffusive-advective transport conditions. Observing Fig. 8a, b and c, it is clear that for a positive pressure gradient and for a fixed deficit observed from Rn measurements, if purely diffusive transport or equilibrium conditions are considered, an underestimation of the actual LNAPL saturations (considered as those of the diffusive-advective curve) is reached. It is also clear that, if Rn measurements are performed at a certain distance from the source, i.e., closer to the surface, the risk of misinterpreting LNAPL saturation increases because the differences between the curves become much more pronounced at shallower depths. By moving the measurement point too far away from the LNAPL source, the deficits become no longer observable with varying saturations, making the technique no longer applicable.

Considering the case of a negative pressure gradient (Fig. 7d–f), it can be observed that the deficit at the source zone in Fig. 7d ($S_N = 5 \%$) for a pressure gradient of -0.05 Pa/m is approximately 0.67. Assuming a diffusion-dominated transport, the same deficit value at the same depth would lead to an estimated LNAPL saturation value of about 7 % (using the nomographs presented by Cecconi et al. (2022)), while under equilibrium conditions it would be around 2 % (using Eq. (13)). Therefore, it can be stated that ignoring the presence of advective transport, assuming it to be purely diffusive, results in an overestimation of LNAPL saturation, while assuming equilibrium conditions leads to an underestimation of LNAPL saturation (see also Fig. 8d, e, f). It can indeed be observed that the Rn deficit curves for negative pressure gradients lie between the

diffusive deficit curve and the deficit value obtained assuming equilibrium conditions. It should be noted again that, also for this scenario, performing Rn measurements in the source zone helps to reduce the uncertainty of the method, since at these depths the curves are significantly closer to each other and to the equilibrium deficit value (see also Fig. 8d, e, f).

Considering instead the variable pressure gradient conditions of Fig. 7g, h and i, it can be observed that diffusion and diffusion-advection deficit

prove to be much closer to each other. In this case the most important deviations occur considering the Rn deficits at higher distances from the source zone (i.e., approaching the surface), where Rn deficit exceeds the value of 1 for some shallow depths (see also Fig. 8i). Obtaining deficit values greater than 1 in the application of the technique would lead not only (as in previous cases) to an erroneous estimation of LNAPL saturations but even to the risk of confusing areas with LNAPL as background areas.

Fig. 7. Rn deficit profiles for different imposed pressure gradients and different LNAPL saturations. Three LNAPL saturation conditions are considered: $S_N = 5\%$ for figures a, d, g; $S_N = 10\%$ for figures b, e, h; and $S_N = 20\%$ for figures c, f, i. Three conditions for the pressure gradient are shown (low, medium, high): a constant positive pressure gradient (+0.01, +0.05, +0.1 Pa/m) (figures a–c), a constant negative pressure gradient (–0.01, –0.05, –0.1 Pa/m) (figures d–f), and a variable pressure gradient in the LNAPL zone, positive (+0.01, +0.05, +0.1 Pa/m) and negative (–0.0025, –0.0125, –0.025 Pa/m) in the upper layer (N_u), compared with a zero pressure gradient in the background area (B) (figures g–i). The deficit profile of the only diffusive transport case is also shown (dashed curve) in each figure. The deficit expected at equilibrium conditions is also reported as a reference. The dotted lines represent the beginning of the layer with LNAPL.

3.4. Influence of site-specific parameters on Rn deficit profiles

The extent of the influence of advective fluxes on Rn transport in soil gas depends on the site-specific parameters. Therefore, the effect of LNAPL composition, soil type, source zone thickness, and groundwater table

depth on the Rn deficit curve was analyzed by considering three different pressure gradient conditions and varying only one of the investigated parameters each time. For each of the pressure gradient conditions (see Fig. 2 and Table 2) considered, in Figs. S1–S4, the diffusive Rn deficit curve and three diffusive-advective deficit curves (calculated for three

Fig. 8. LNAPL saturation – Rn deficit curves for different imposed pressure gradients and different vertical distances from the water table. Three distances between the soil gas Rn measuring point and the water table: a zero distance (i.e., at the water table) for figures a, d, g; a distance of 1 m for figures b, e, h; and of 4 m for figures c, f, i. Three conditions for the pressure gradient are shown: a constant positive pressure gradient (figures a–c), a constant negative pressure gradient (figures d–f), and a variable pressure gradient in the LNAPL zone, positive in the LNAPL source zone and negative in the upper layer, compared with a zero pressure gradient in the background area (figures g–i). The colored area indicates the variation of the diffusion-advection curve when varying the pressure gradient intensity from a lower to a higher value (see Table 2), while the curve at the middle of the area represents a medium value (see Table 2). The curve of the only diffusive transport case is also shown (dashed curve) in each figure. The deficit expected at equilibrium conditions is also reported as a reference.

pressure gradient values: a lower, an intermediate and a higher value) will be shown in each graph. It was found that the parameter to have the greatest influence on Rn deficit profiles is soil type (Fig. S2), since the effect of advection results important for coarse-grained rather than fine-grained soils, and, at a lower extent, also LNAPL composition (Fig. S1). Instead, both the source zone thickness (Fig. S3) and the water table depth (Fig. S4) do not seem to significantly influence the Rn deficit values measured at a certain distance from the water table, even in the presence of a pressure gradient in the subsurface, considering the same pressure gradient simulation scenario. A more detailed discussion is given in the Supplementary Material.

4. Conclusions

The analysis carried out in this work highlighted that for most of the simulated conditions, advective phenomena in the subsurface can significantly influence the Rn profiles and deficits in the subsurface compared to the ones expected assuming a diffusion-dominated transport or assuming equilibrium conditions.

Advection can be neglected when the Peclet number is lower than 1, and thus a purely diffusive transport model can be applied. In these cases, LNAPL saturation can be estimated using the nomograms provided by Cecconi et al. (2022). For higher values of the Peclet number, i.e., in cases where the influence of advective transport is comparable to or greater than diffusive transport, Rn deficit profiles are strongly influenced by local advection. In particular, it was found that in high-permeability soils (such as sandy soils), in the presence of local advective fluxes in the same direction of diffusive fluxes (e.g., in the case of a rising groundwater level), the Rn deficit can be higher than would be expected in the presence of a diffusion-dominated transport. This implies that in those cases, applying the Rn deficit technique neglecting advection can lead to an underestimation of the expected LNAPL saturation in the subsurface. This underestimation becomes more significant when the traditional Rn deficit technique (assuming equilibrium condition) is applied to soil gas Rn measurements carried out at some vertical distance from the LNAPL source zone. Assuming the occurrence of local advective fluxes in the opposite direction of diffusive fluxes (e.g., in the case of a falling water table), the observed Rn deficit is expected to be smaller than that in the case of diffusion-dominated transport, but higher than the one expected under equilibrium conditions. This implies that in those cases, applying the Rn deficit technique neglecting advection can lead to overestimations of the expected LNAPL saturation in the subsurface, while applying the traditional Rn deficit technique, assuming equilibrium conditions, there is a tendency to slightly underestimate LNAPL saturation values. In both cases, by approaching the Rn measurement point to the depths of the LNAPL source zone, the error in saturation estimation can be significantly reduced. Furthermore, in the case of the occurrence of methanogenesis processes in the LNAPL zone, a local advection can be expected only in the LNAPL-impacted zone (with a positive pressure gradient in the source zone and a negative pressure gradient in the overlying layer) and not in the adjacent areas considered for Rn background values. In such cases, the differences in deficit profiles can be so significant as to make the Rn deficit greater than 1, thus risking, on a practical level, a complete misinterpretation of Rn monitoring data. Even in this case, this confounding effect can be significantly reduced if soil gas Rn measurements are performed in the proximity of the LNAPL source and thus at greater depths compared to typical soil gas analysis performed at depths of around 1 m. In this regard Rn concentrations in soil gas could be measured directly within the source zone, using the headspace of groundwater monitoring wells (typically screened across the water table, thus in the LNAPL source zone), as already proposed for other applications (e.g., see Sweeney and Todd Ririe, 2017). This approach could be used as an alternative to measurements in permanent or temporary soil gas probes, which typically do not allow for measurements at depths greater than 1.5–2 m (although greater depths can be reached in some cases depending on soil type). Namely, this option can be particularly indicated to assess and monitor the evolution of LNAPL contamination in

the occurrence of natural source zone depletion processes or during active remediation. In any case, when using the model proposed in this work, attention must be paid to the site conditions being simulated, considering the different assumptions on which the analytical model is based (e.g., steady-state conditions, homogeneity of soil and contamination in the domain layers, and homogeneity of other site-specific parameters such as Rn production, diffusion coefficient or water content). For sites with pronounced heterogeneities, it may be more indicated to use a numerical model that better simulates these conditions, such as the one provided in this paper (modified from Barrio-Parra et al. (2022)).

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Alessandra Cecconi: Methodology, Data curation, Writing - Original draft preparation. **Iason Verginelli:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Supervision, Writing - Original draft preparation. **Fernando Barrio-Parra:** Methodology, Writing - Review and Editing. **Eduardo De Miguel:** Writing - Review and Editing, Supervision. **Renato Baciocchi:** Writing - Review and Editing, Supervision.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Details regarding the assessment of the influence of site-specific parameters on Rn deficit profiles, and the estimation of permeability parameters are available in the Supplementary Material 1.

The full Matlab® code, modified from Barrio-Parra et al. (2022), used for comparison with the analytical solution is available in the Supplementary Material 2, together with the files needed to run the simulations. Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.162619>.

References

- Alzaydi, A.A., Moore, C.A., Rai, I.S., 1978. Combined pressure and diffusional transition region flow of gases in porous media. *AIChE J.* 24 (1), 35–43.
- Amos, R.T., Mayer, K.U., Bekins, B.A., Delin, G.N., Williams, R.L., 2005. Use of dissolved and vapor-phase gases to investigate methanogenic degradation of petroleum hydrocarbon contamination in the subsurface. *Water Resour. Res.* 41 (2).
- API, 2000. Non Aqueous Phase Liquid (NAPL) Mobility Limits in soil. *Soil & Groundwater Research Bulletin* No.9.
- Auer, L.H., Rosenberg, N.D., Birdsell, K.H., Whitney, E.M., 1996. The effects of barometric pumping on contaminant transport. *J. Contam. Hydrol.* 24 (2), 145–166.
- Barbosa, E.Q., Galhardi, J.A., Bonotto, D.M., 2014. The use of radon (Rn-222) and volatile organic compounds in monitoring soil gas to localize NAPL contamination at a gas station in Rio Claro, São Paulo State, Brazil. *Radiat. Meas.* 66, 1–4.
- Barrio-Parra, F., Izquierdo-Díaz, M., Díaz-Curiel, J., De Miguel, E., 2021. Field performance of the radon-deficit technique to detect and delineate a complex DNAPL accumulation in a multi-layer soil profile. *Environ. Pollut.* 269, 116200.
- Barrio-Parra, F., Hidalgo, A., Izquierdo-Díaz, M., Arévalo-Lomas, L., De Miguel, E., 2022. 1D-RnDPM: a freely available ²²²Rn production, diffusion, and partition model to evaluate confounding factors in the radon-deficit technique. *Sci. Total Environ.* 807, 150815.
- Castelluccio, M., Agrahari, S., De Simone, G., Pompili, F., Lucchetti, C., Sengupta, D., Galli, G., Friello, P., Curatolo, P., Giorgi, R., Tuccimei, P., 2018. Using a multi-method approach based on soil radon deficit, resistivity, and induced polarization measurements to monitor non-aqueous phase liquid contamination in two study areas in Italy and India. *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* 25 (13), 12515–12527.
- Cavelan, A., Golfier, F., Colombano, S., Davarzani, H., Deparis, J., Faure, P., 2022. A critical review of the influence of groundwater level fluctuations and temperature on LNAPL contaminations in the context of climate change. *Sci. Total Environ.* 806, 150412.
- Cecconi, A., Verginelli, I., Baciocchi, R., 2022. Modeling of soil gas radon as an in situ partitioning tracer for quantifying LNAPL contamination. *Sci. Total Environ.* 806, 150593.

- Choi, J.W., Smith, J.A., 2005. Geoenvironmental factors affecting organic vapor advection and diffusion fluxes from the unsaturated zone to the atmosphere under natural conditions. *Environ. Eng. Sci.* 22 (1), 95–108.
- CL:AIRE, 2014. An Illustrated Handbook of LNAPL Transport and Fate in the Subsurface. CL:AIRE, London. <http://www.claire.co.uk/LNAPL>.
- Clever, H.L. (Ed.), 1979. Solubility Data Series. Vol 2: Krypton, Xenon and Radon - Gas Solubilities. International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry, Pergamon Press, UK.
- Cohen, G., Jousse, F., Luze, N., Höhener, P., Atteia, O., 2016. LNAPL source zone delineation using soil gases in a heterogeneous silty-sand aquifer. *J. Contam. Hydrol.* 192, 20–34.
- Cohen, G.J., Bernachot, I., Su, D., Höhener, P., Mayer, K.U., Atteia, O., 2019. Laboratory-scale experimental and modelling investigations of 222Rn profiles in chemically heterogeneous LNAPL contaminated vadose zones. *Sci. Total Environ.* 681, 456–466.
- CRC CARE, 2018. Technical measurement guidance for LNAPL natural source zone depletion. CRC CARE Technical Report no. 44, CRC for Contamination Assessment and Remediation of the Environment, Newcastle, Australia.
- Cunningham, R.E., Williams, R.J.J., 1980. Diffusion in Gases and Porous Media Vol. 1. Plenum press, New York.
- Davis, B.M., Istok, J.D., Semprini, L., 2005. Numerical simulations of radon as an in situ partitioning tracer for quantifying NAPL contamination using push-pull tests. *J. Contam. Hydrol.* 78 (1–2), 87–103.
- De Miguel, E., Barrio-Parra, F., Elío, J., Izquierdo-Díaz, M., García-González, J.E., Mazadiego, L.F., Medina, R., 2018. Applicability of radon emanometry in lithologically discontinuous sites contaminated by organic chemicals. *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* 25, 20255–20263.
- De Miguel, E., Barrio-Parra, F., Izquierdo-Díaz, M., Fernández, J., García-González, J.E., Álvarez, R., 2020. Applicability and limitations of the radon-deficit technique for the preliminary assessment of sites contaminated with complex mixtures of organic chemicals: a blind field-test. *Environ. Int.* 138, 105591.
- De Simone, G., Lucchetti, C., Pompili, F., Galli, G., Tuccimei, P., Curatolo, P., Giorgi, R., 2017. Soil radon survey to assess NAPL contamination from an ancient spill. Do kerosene vapors affect radon partition? *J. Environ. Radioact.* 171, 138–147.
- Fan, K., Kuo, T., Han, Y., CC, Lin, C., Lee, C., 2007. Radon distribution in a gasoline-contaminated aquifer. *Radiat. Meas.* 42 (3), 479–485.
- Forde, O.N., Cahill, A.G., Beckie, R.D., Mayer, K.U., 2019. Barometric-pumping controls fugitive gas emissions from a vadose zone natural gas release. *Sci. Rep.* 9 (1), 1–9.
- García-González, J., Ortega, M., Chacón, E., Mazadiego, L., Miguel, E.D., 2008. Field validation of radon monitoring as a screening methodology for NAPL-contaminated sites. *Appl. Geochem.* 23 (9), 2753–2758.
- Hillel, D., 1982. Introduction to soil physics. Academic Press, inc, California, USA, p. 364.
- Höhener, P., Surbeck, H., 2004. Radon-222 as a tracer for nonaqueous phase liquid in the vadose zone: experiments and analytical model. *Vadose Zone J.* 3 (4), 1276–1285.
- Hunkeler, D., Hoehn, E., Höhener, P., Zeyer, J., 1997. Rn-222 as a partitioning tracer to detect diesel fuel contamination in aquifers: laboratory study and field observations. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 31, 3180–3187.
- ITRC (Interstate Technology & Regulatory Council), 2009. Evaluating Natural Source Zone Depletion at Sites with LNAPL. LNAPL-1. Interstate Technology & Regulatory Council, LNAPLs Team, Washington, D.C.. www.itrcweb.org.
- ITRC (Interstate Technology & Regulatory Council), 2018. Light Non-aqueous Phase Liquids (LNAPL) Document Update, LNAPL-3. Interstate Technology & Regulatory Council, LNAPL Update Team, Washington, USA.
- ITRC (Interstate Technology & Regulatory Council), 2019. Implementing Advanced Site Characterization Tools. ASCT-1. Washington, D.C.: Interstate Technology & Regulatory Council, Advanced Site Characterization Tools Team. <https://asct-1.itrcweb.org>.
- Le Meur, M., Cohen, G.J.V., Laurent, M., Höhener, P., Atteia, O., 2021. Effect of NAPL mixture and alteration on m-222 partitioning coefficients: implications for NAPL subsurface contamination quantification. *Sci. Total Environ.* 791, 148210.
- Lundegard, P.D., Johnson, P.C., 2006. Source zone natural attenuation at petroleum hydrocarbon spill sites—II: application to a former oil field. *Groundwater Monit. Rem.* 26 (4), 93–106.
- Ma, J., Rixey, W.G., DeVaul, G.E., Stafford, B.P., Alvarez, P.J., 2012. Methane bioattenuation and implications for explosion risk reduction along the groundwater to soil surface pathway above a plume of dissolved ethanol. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 46 (11), 6013–6019.
- Ma, J., Luo, H., DeVaul, G.E., Rixey, W.G., Alvarez, P.J., 2014. Numerical model investigation for potential methane explosion and benzene vapor intrusion associated with high-ethanol blend releases. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 48 (1), 474–481.
- Man, J., Wang, G., Chen, Q., Yao, Y., 2021. Investigating the role of vadose zone breathing in vapor intrusion from contaminated groundwater. *J. Hazard. Mater.* 416, 126272.
- Massmann, J., Farrier, D.F., 1992. Effects of atmospheric pressures on gas transport in the vadose zone. *Water Resour. Res.* 28 (3), 777–791.
- Mateus, C., Pecequillo, B.R., 2015. Preliminary results of NAPL contamination in a disused industry in the city of São Paulo, Brazil, by random evaluation with CR-39 detectors. International Nuclear Atlantic Conference. ASSOCIAÇÃO BRASILEIRA DE ENERGIA NUCLEAR - ABEN, São Paulo, SP, Brazil.
- Millington, R.J., Quirk, J.P., 1961. Permeability of porous solids. *Trans. Faraday Soc.* 57, 1200–1207.
- Molins, S., Mayer, K.U., 2007. Coupling between geochemical reactions and multicomponent gas and solute transport in unsaturated media: a reactive transport modeling study. *Water Resour. Res.* 43 (5).
- Molins, S., Mayer, K.U., Amos, R.T., Bekins, B.A., 2010. Vadose zone attenuation of organic compounds at a crude oil spill site—Interactions between biogeochemical reactions and multicomponent gas transport. *J. Contam. Hydrol.* 112 (1–4), 15–29.
- Nazaroff, W.W., Moed, B.A., Sextro, R.G., Revzan, K.L., Nero, A.V., 1989. Factors Influencing Soil as a Source of Indoor Radon: Framework for Assessing Radon Source Potential.
- Nazaroff, W.W., 1992. Radon transport from soil to air. *Rev. Geophys.* 30 (2), 137–160.
- Newell, C., Acree, S., Ross, R., Huling, S., 1995. Light nonaqueous phase liquids. *Ground Water Issue*, US EPA/540/S-95-500. United States Environmental Protection Agency, Washington, DC.
- Neznal, M., Matolin, M., Just, G., Turek, K., 2004. Short-term temporal variations of soil gas radon concentration and comparison of measurement techniques. *Radiat. Prot. Dosim.* 108 (1), 55–63.
- Ng, G.H.C., Bekins, B.A., Cozzarelli, I.M., Baedecker, M.J., Bennett, P.C., Amos, R.T., Herkelrath, W.N., 2015. Reactive transport modeling of geochemical controls on secondary water quality impacts at a crude oil spill site near Bemidji, MN. *Water Resour. Res.* 51 (6), 4156–4183.
- Qi, S., Luo, J., O'Connor, D., Cao, X., Hou, D., 2020. Influence of groundwater table fluctuation on the non-equilibrium transport of volatile organic contaminants in the vadose zone. *J. Hydrol.* 580, 124353.
- Sakoda, A., Ishimori, Y., Yamaoka, K., 2011. A comprehensive review of radon emanation measurements for mineral, rock, soil, mill tailing and fly ash. *Appl. Radiat. Isot.* 69 (10), 1422–1435.
- Scanlon, B.R., Nicot, J.P., Massmann, J.W., 2002. Soil gas movement in unsaturated systems. *Soil Phys. Companion* 389, 297–341.
- Schubert, M., Freyer, K., Treutler, H.C., Weiß, H., 2001. Using the soil gas radon as an indicator for ground contamination by non-aqueous phase-liquids. *J. Soils Sediments* 1 (4), 217–222.
- Schubert, M., Freyer, K., Weiss, H., Treutler, H.C., 2002. Using radon-222 in soil gas as an indicator of subsurface contamination by non-aqueous phase-liquids (NAPLs). *Geofis. Int.* 41 (4), 433–437.
- Schubert, M., Pena, P., Balcazar, M., Meissner, R., Lopez, A., Flores, J., 2005. Determination of radon distribution patterns in the upper soil as a tool for the localization of subsurface NAPL contamination. *Radiat. Meas.* 40 (2–6), 633–637.
- Schubert, M., Lehmann, K., Paschke, A., 2007. Determination of radon partition coefficients between water and organic liquids and their utilization for the assessment of subsurface NAPL contamination. *Sci. Total Environ.* 376 (1–3), 306–316.
- Schubert, M., 2015. Using radon as environmental tracer for the assessment of subsurface non-aqueous phase liquid (NAPL) contamination - a review. *Eur. Phys. J. Spec. Top.* 224 (4), 717–730.
- Semprini, L., Hopkins, O., Tasker, B., 2000. Laboratory, field and modeling studies of radon-222 as a natural tracer for monitoring NAPL contamination. *Transp. Porous Media* 38 (1–2), 223–240.
- Sweeney, R.E., Todd Ririe, G., 2017. Small purge method to sample vapor from groundwater monitoring wells screened across the water table. *Groundwater Monit. Rem.* 37 (4), 51–59.
- Thorntson, D.C., Pollock, D.W., 1989. Gas transport in unsaturated zones: multicomponent systems and the adequacy of Fick's laws. *Water Resour. Res.* 25 (3), 477–507.
- U.S. EPA, 2004. User's guide for evaluating subsurface vapor intrusion into buildings. Washington, DC, 204602004. https://www.epa.gov/sites/default/files/201511/documents/2004_0222_3phase_users_guide.pdf.
- U.S. EPA, 2015. Technical guide for addressing petroleum vapor intrusion at leaking underground storage tank sites, U.S. Environmental Protection Agency: Washington, DC. <https://www.epa.gov/sites/default/files/2015-06/documents/pvi-guide-final-6-10-15.pdf>.
- Van der Spoel, W.H., Van der Graaf, E.R., De Meijer, R.J., 1997. Diffusive transport of radon in a homogeneous column of dry sand. *Health Phys.* 72 (5), 766–778.
- Verginelli, I., Baciocchi, R., 2021. Refinement of the gradient method for the estimation of natural source zone depletion at petroleum contaminated sites. *J. Contam. Hydrol.* 241, 103807.
- Werner, D., Höhener, P., 2002. Diffusive partitioning tracer test for nonaqueous phase liquid (NAPL) detection in the vadose zone. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 36 (7), 1592–1599.
- Yao, Y., Wu, Y., Wang, Y., Verginelli, I., Zeng, T., Suuberg, E.M., Jiang, L., Wen, Y., Ma, J., 2015. A petroleum vapor intrusion model involving upward advective soil gas flow due to methane generation. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 49 (19), 11577–11585.